

IMPLEMENTATION OF MULTI-CHANNEL DISTRIBUTION AS AN ALTERNATIVE MARKETING BREED-FREE CHICKEN TO INCREASE THE INCOME OF FARMERS' HOUSEHOLDS IN SOUTH SULAWESI

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Abstract

This research aims to provide understanding to fishermen as free-range chicken producers and marketing institutions about which marketing channels provide higher income levels than other channels. Furthermore, this research also aims to increase knowledge for free-range chicken producers to carry out product diversification, so that the added value of chicken prices is higher. With product improvements, of course free-range chicken producers will increase their business partners and in the end sales volume will increase and business profits will also increase. This product diversification step is a manifestation of a change in producer behavior from catching directly selling (TLJ) to picking and selling behavior (POL). The results of this research found that the income received by marketing institutions involved in the free-range chicken trade was influenced by the marketing functions carried out. The behavior of marketing institutions in each channel where the sales price of tailed chickens to consumers increased on average between 17.50% to 30.67%. The increase in selling prices for each institution is due to the treatment of the marketing function, among others; transportation functions, advertising, cleaning, maintenance, and so on. With the existence of alternative marketing of free-range chickens as a marketing activity to distribute from breeders to final consumers with the aim of getting more expensive economic value. Collecting traders selling free-range chickens to retailers have incurred costs for several marketing functions, as well as other marketing institutions so that the price paid by final consumers is more expensive. The conclusion is that the longer the chicken marketing distribution channel tends to be more expensive than the short marketing channel. However, you need to know that the application of marketing channels, both long and short, is influenced by the characteristics of the product being marketed.

Keywords: Business Behavior, Distribution Channels, Breeder Income.

INTRODUCTION

National development is carried out with the aim of achieving several targets at once, namely self-sufficiency in the livestock sector, increasing foreign exchange earnings, increasing wider employment opportunities, increasing the income of the Pengajaran Islands community and

utilizing and preserving natural resources nationally. Pangkep Regency was the area chosen because the area is known as a source of livelihood for its people, the dominant of which is the cultivation of free-range chickens. The average annual increase in production reached 2.11%. And or increased by an average of 203,024.62 tons/year

The production of free-range chickens is increasing from year to year, of course this is an opportunity for marketing institutions to become marketing intermediaries from producers to final consumers in the hope of getting services through marketing margins.

Increasing production as a concept is not only seen from activities to increase the number of products physically produced, but all activities that add value to goods and services including the marketing system which is the lifeblood of a business mechanism (A. Harizt. 2001. p. 68) . as experienced by producers (breeders) is that production increases, but the sales value is often not significant with the level of income received.

The product marketing system in the livestock business sector is a very complex system, especially since there is the involvement of intermediary institutions (marketing institutions) to market it, each of which has different interests and methods. Methods and methods for marketing chickens from breeders to final consumers certainly require quite a lot of money.

The costs incurred by both livestock producers and marketing institutions will affect the high cost of goods sold and the selling price that consumers must pay. According to Kenneth, Kenneth, (2011), the amount of marketing costs differs from one another because; types of commodities, marketing locations, types and number of marketing institutions and the effectiveness of the marketing carried out

Marketing treatment as above directly harms breeders/households that breed free-range chickens as the main source of income in the free-range chicken farming business. The marketing process from breeder producers to final consumers requires various functional marketing activities aimed at expediting the process of distributing goods (free range chickens) effectively and efficiently to meet consumer needs and desires.

The final consumers referred to here are local, regional consumers and entrepreneurs between villages and villages who are deemed to need chickens, especially during sacrificial holidays. The marketing function is carried out by marketing institutions that are related or involved in the marketing process of free-range chicken which forms a marketing chain or is often referred to as a marketing system.

Pangkep Regency is a research location where there are several marketing institutions involved in the fish trade mechanism, namely; local retail traders, Ponggawa (collecting traders including cooperatives), sub-district intermediary traders as agents, district wholesalers, inter-island wholesalers and exporter wholesalers.

Marketing institutions involved in commodity trading have two functions, namely as buyers and sellers, so that in this pair relationship there is a sales function on the one hand and a buyer function on the other.

The occurrence of these two functions of marketing institutions illustrates the transfer of property rights or control rights by each institution to the chicken commodity, thereby causing an increase in the use of ownership.

The mechanism for buying and selling chicken commodities from breeders to intermediary traders (marketing institutions) consists of three types of transaction behavior, namely; (1) active-active type, namely each active between the seller (producer) and buyer, and usually this type occurs when fishermen have a production volume equal to demand, (2) active-passive type, namely active producers offering their production results due to an increase in production output, but buyers are less active, and usually this type occurs when supply is greater than demand, as a result prices are determined more by buyers including marketing institutions, (3) passive-active type, which is the opposite of the second type above, where buyers are more active in demanding goods (fish) and sellers (producers) are less active, which may be due to reduced production results, and usually the prevailing prices are more influenced by producers.

The buying and selling function, which is usually called the exchange function, is very important to reduce barriers to the transfer of property rights in an effort to provide satisfaction to consumers by considering effective and efficient marketing channels.

By changing the ownership status of goods through the exchange function an, then the above activities function to add value to ownership of the product. The final consumer will be willing to pay a certain amount of money equal to the value of the product, if the product is perceived and able to provide a satisfaction value commensurate with the money that must be spent, including service and product quality.

Fish trade with market quality standards is largely determined by the end consumer, so the role of marketing institutions is very necessary because the marketing function is mostly carried out by marketing institutions because they have sufficient capital to do so. With the costs incurred to meet the quality standards desired by consumers, the selling price is also influenced, or in other words, the price paid by consumers is more expensive than consumers going directly to producers (breeders).

Marketing functions related to product quality include sorting/cleaning, storage, cooling, packing and transportation activities. Meanwhile, others include disciplined management and maintenance of business facilities and infrastructure so that product waste/damage does not occur. According to Avonina, S. (2010), the amount of marketing costs differs from one another because; types of commodities, marketing locations, types and number of marketing institutions and the effectiveness of the marketing carried out.

The high basic price that consumers have to pay will reduce the level of consumption and real income of consumers and consumers will tend to think of alternative ways of substituting spending for the goods they want to buy, such as buying tailed chickens from breeders at expensive prices, it is better to buy tofu/tempeh or eggs at an affordable price and high nutritional value.

Objective

- 1) To understand the marketing system for free-range chickens from breeders to final consumers.
- 2) To determine the role of marketing institutions involved in the process of transitioning free-range free-range chicken production from breeders to final consumers.
- 3) To determine the marketing margin and level of marketing efficiency at each marketing institution and its channels.

Meanwhile, the benefit of this study is that it is hoped that it can be used as consideration for the government in making decisions regarding development in the livestock sector, especially policies for developing native/free-range chicken farming businesses as people's livestock.

RESEARCH METHODS

1. Research Location

The research was conducted in two districts, namely Pangkep Regency and Maros Regency, South Sulawesi Province with the basis for choosing this location because these two areas are supplier areas for free-range chicken farming products which are known as free-range/free-range chicken farming centers among other areas. And another reason is that the majority of people depend on this sector for their livelihood, namely around 56.27% on average (source, BPS South Sulawesi Province in Figures 2023). Then, it is hoped that these two areas will be designated as research objects in the future, when the results of the research will be taken into consideration by the local government in preparing short and medium term development plans.

2. Population and Sample

The population in this study was to select several farmer-fisherman groups from both regions which had a minimum of 5-10 members. Based on statistical data for each of these two regions, 78 free-range chicken breeder groups have been recorded, which means they have a membership population of ± 624 people, and if each member has a minimum of 3 family members, this means the number of people living in this sector is 1872 soul.

3. Types and Sources of Data

The data obtained in this research includes primary data sourced from empirical data directly collected from the research location through direct observation, interviews and distributing questionnaires. The next data is secondary data obtained through reviewing the literature in the form of books, journals and required documents related to the research.

4. Data Collection Techniques

The technique used to obtain data is to use several methods, namely; interviews, distributing questionnaires, and literature studies. The data collection method by distributing questionnaires is intended to find out and compile data about the production volume of free-range chickens and the sales value received as well as the level of profit after expenses for the production

factors used. Meanwhile, the data obtained through interviews is how many marketing institutions are their business partners. and to what extent the level of marketing efficiency is relative to the chosen marketing channels. Meanwhile, data obtained through literature studies, journals and so on is knowledge that has research relevance.

5. Data analysis

Based on the data obtained from the research results, the following analysis can be made:

1. Marketing margin.

To measure the size of the marketing margin at each marketing institution by the channels through which the product reaches the final consumer are:

$$M = B + \pi$$

Where:

M = Marketing margin

B = Marketing costs

Π = Profit

(Steven, 2011)

The total marketing margin can be determined by adding up the margins for each marketing institution involved in marketing free-range chickens, namely:

$$M = Y1 + Y2 + Y3 + \dots + Yn$$

Where:

M = Total margin

Y1 = Marketing margin at market level 1

Y2 = Marketing margin at market level 2

Y3 = Marketing margin at market level 3

Yn = Marketing margin at market level n

To calculate the profits of marketing institutions, a formula is used:

$$\Pi = TR - TC$$

Where:

Π = Benefits of each marketing agency involved.

TR = Total revenue (total revenue for each marketing institution

TC = Total costs incurred by marketing institutions.

1. Marketing Efficiency

To measure the level of marketing efficiency, a formula is used:

$$EP = \frac{\text{Marketing costs}}{\text{The value of the product being marketed}} \times 100 \%$$

2. Analysis of factors that influence marketing margins

To find out the factors that influence marketing margins, multiple regression analysis was carried out using the formula :

$$Y = b_0 + b_1X_1 + b_2X_2 + E_i$$

Where :

Y = Marketing margin

X1 = Marketing costs

X2 = Marketing advantages

b₀ = Parameters to be estimated

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

1. Post-Marketing Treatment of Free-range Chicken

In order for the quality and smooth marketing of free-range chickens, which is a routine business for fishing communities in Pangkep Regency, the marketing concept is the main factor that influences the income level of farmers and needs special attention, so that the price received by free-range chicken farmers remains reasonable, so post-marketing treatment is a very important role.

In Pangkep Regency as a research focus on free-range chicken farming business management, especially studies on the behavior of marketing institutions which influence the level of income of free-range chicken breeders and provide an illustration that post-marketing activities are carried out by free-range chicken breeders only at the initial stage, namely farmers only carry out maintenance. to post-harvest, transportation and sales in tail form. Meanwhile, the sorting, cleaning, promotion, packing and transportation stages are generally carried out by marketing agencies.

To carry out efficient post-marketing, free-range chicken breeders must change their marketing pattern from mono-channel to multi-channel. The findings obtained in this study are the existence of a mono-channel marketing system, where some farmers have regular subscriptions to intermediary traders who are usually called ponggawa, where this institution provides capital/loans to fishermen who need it first with a business contract for fish produced by free-range chickens. sold to the intermediary trader.

For details on post-marketing treatment of free-range chickens, see the following chart:

Figure 1: Post-Marketing Treatment of Free-range Chicken

Post-marketing activities are generally carried out by marketing institutions, including retailers, collecting traders, wholesalers, agents and inter-island traders with more work being done by their workforce. Meanwhile, breeders as producers of tailed chickens prefer to sell them directly to intermediaries or marketing institutions and carry out less marketing functions. This is done because breeders have several limitations such as; time and costs to carry out the marketing process, so that the price paid by breeders from intermediary traders is not significant in relation to the income received.

Marketing in principle is the flow of chickens from producers to consumers. This flow of goods can occur because of the role of marketing institutions, where the role of these institutions is very dependent on the prevailing market system and the characteristics of the flow of goods being marketed. Therefore, this concept is often termed marketing channels, whose function is very important, especially in looking at price levels in each marketing institution.

Table 1: Activities of marketing functions carried out at various levels of behavior of fresh sea fish marketing institutions

No.	Behavior	Activity
01.	Chicken breeders Not purebred	- <i>Post-harvest chickens</i> - <i>Storage</i> - <i>Maintenance</i> - <i>Transportation</i> - <i>Sale</i>
02.	Collector traders	- <i>Purchases</i> - <i>Cleaning</i> - <i>Preservation</i> - <i>Transportation</i> - <i>Sale</i>
03.	Wholesalers	- <i>Purchasing</i> - <i>Sorting</i> - <i>Preservation</i> - <i>Packing</i> - <i>Transportation</i> - <i>Sales</i>
04.	Retailer	- <i>Purchasing</i> - <i>Sorting</i> - <i>Preservation</i> - <i>Sale</i>

Table 1. above, it can be seen that post-marketing activities by implementing marketing functions are generally carried out by marketing institutions so that the costs incurred directly increase, thus affecting the total cost per unit of product/fish. In this description, it appears that in the marketing process from producer to final consumer, marketing institutions have an important role in the free-range chicken trade which has benefits and interests for all parties, including increasing local income and employment opportunities.

2. Marketing Channels

Marketing of free-range chickens, which are usually called fresh live chickens, in Pangkep Regency, there are several marketing institutions in the process of being transferred from producers to final consumers. There are several traders/intermediary marketing institutions involved in the marketing process, namely; (1) collecting traders/pongawa, (2) commissioners, (3) wholesalers, (4) retailers/pagangang to final consumers.

Free-range chicken breeders as Kamoung chicken producers generally look for chickens in villages or villages of free-range chicken breeders in the run-up to sacrificial holidays and other holidays by collecting, storing, transporting and then selling them to marketing institutions/intermediary traders in live bird doses.

For more details, the marketing channels for free-range chickens in Pangkep Regency are the marketing institutions for final consumers. Business costs and income. The free-range chicken

commodity in the livestock sector is the main source of income for the majority of the population of Pangkep Regency, where this area is known as one of the areas that has many villages keeping free-range chickens, hence the name free-range chicken center. The marketing channels used by the free-range chicken trade in Pangkep Regency are as follows:

Picture 2: Marketing channels for free-range chickens

Channel I

Analysis of costs, margins and profits on this channel can be seen in table 2. Below:

Table 2: Analysis of costs, margins and income at collector level traders (Rp/head)

No.	Description	Types of Chickens		
		Ras	Broiler	Not race
01.	Purchases	22.500	17.500	9.100
02.	Marketing costs: :			
	•Transport	2.500	1.750	910
	•Cleaning	1.500	1.225	637
	•Sorting	1.350	875	364
	•Preservation	1.125	700	0
	•Packing	2.250	525	0
	•Storage	0	350	0
03.	Total costs	8.725	5.425	1.911
04.	Cost price	31.225	22.925	11.011
05.	Sales price	37.470	28.656	14.314
06.	Income	6.245	5.731	3.303
07.	Marketing margin	14.970	11.156	5.214
08.	Mark-up	20,540	25,190	30,320

Source: Primary data after processing

Table 2. Above provides an illustration of the income received by intermediary traders/collectors, there are several types of fish that do not carry out marketing functions, but this does not affect the level of income but tends to increase, such as for free-range chickens and broilers. The behavior of marketing/collecting institutions in this channel has determined sales prices to increase between 17.50% to 30.67%. Furthermore, the analysis of costs, margins and income for sub-district wholesalers can be seen in table 3 below:

Table 3: Analysis of Costs, Margins and Income at the District Wholesaler Level (Rp/head)

No.	Description	Types of Chickens		
		Ras	Broiler	Not race
01.	Purchases	37.470	28.656	14.314
02.	Marketing costs:			
	•Transport	2.500	1.750	910
	• Cleaning	-	-	668
	• Sorting	1.417	918	382
	• Preservation	1.181	735	715
	• Packing	2.362	551	750
	• Storage	374	357	286
03.	Total costs	7.834	4.311	3.711
04.	Cost price	45.304	32.967	18.025
05.	Sales price	49.834	36.263	19.828
06.	Income	4.530	3.296	1.803
07.	Marketing margin	12.364	7.607	5.514
08.	Mark-up	10,000	12,32	10,020

Source: *Primary data after processing*

Table 3 above contains several treatments for the types of fish processed by sub-district wholesalers which are related to marketing functions such as sorting and packing activities so that the costs incurred by these marketing institutions quite influence the level of income. Then, these wholesalers make sales margins to district/city wholesalers of between 10% and 15.59%.

When compared with the activities of marketing functions between collecting traders and sub-district wholesalers, more collectors do it, so there is a difference in the percentage increase in selling prices, in this case the higher amount received by collectors. Furthermore, analysis of costs, margins and income levels for district/city wholesalers can be seen in table 4 below:

Table 4: Analysis of Costs, Margins and Income for Regency Wholesalers (Rp/head)
Sumber: Data primer setelah diolah

No.	Description	Types of Chickens		
		Ras	Broiler	Not race
01.	Purchases	49.834	36.263	19.828
02.	Marketing costs:			
	•Transport	2.750	1.925	910
	• Cleaning	2.493	1.813	701
	• Sorting	1.445	963	401
	• Preservation	997	725	715
	• Packing	498	557	758
	• Storage	382	363	292
03.	Total costs	8.565	6.346	3.133
04.	Cost price	58.399	42.609	22.961
05.	Sales price	63.655	46.870	25.716
06.	Income	5.256	4.261	2.755
07.	Marketing margin	13.821	10.607	6.888
08.	Mark-up	9,19	11,19	15,00

Table 4 above describes marketing activities to sub-district wholesalers, namely after purchasing fresh sea fish from collectors then carrying out several marketing function activities by paying different amounts of total costs for each type of fish.

The difference in total costs incurred directly affects the level of income and margin received by sub-district wholesalers, however, the mark-up level is between 9.19% and 15%. Paying attention to the results of the analysis of expenditure and income obtained by this marketing institution is not too far from that of collecting traders.

Based on the results of an interview with the head of the farmer group in Pangkep Regency, Dg. Jamal, he said that the price increase for consumers, both industry, retailers and household consumers, was not too high, with an average of 12%. Furthermore, analysis of costs, margins and income at retail level traders can be seen in table 5 below:

Table 5: Cost, Margin and Income Analysis at the Retailer Level for 3 types of pet chickens in Pangkep Regency

No.	Description	Types of Chickens		
		Ras	Broiler	Not race
01.	Purchases	53.655	46.870	75.716
02.	Marketing costs :			
	•Transport	638	469	257
	• Cleaning	0	0	0
	• Sorting	0	0	0
	• Preservation	1.007	732	722
	• Packing	0	0	0
	• Retribution	1.200	1.200	1.200
03.	Total cost	2.845	2.401	2.179
04.	Cost price	56.500	49.271	27.895
05.	Sales price	73.150	64.198	93.474
06.	Income	16.650	14 927	65.579
07.	Marketing margin	19.495	11,300	23.09
08.	Mark-up	11,000	12,120	14,320

Source: Primary data after processing

Table 5 above, after processing the results data on marketing activities carried out by retailers, has obtained analysis results, namely, where this marketing institution (retailer) has three marketing activities carried out, namely; transportation of goods, preservation, and levies and all three incur costs as described in table 5. Then, with the expenditure paid to these three marketing functions, the level of income obtained by retailers decreases so it can be concluded that the more marketing functions are carried out by marketing institutions then the costs of the marketing process also increase so that the retailer's income/profit level decreases.

Channel II

In the marine fish marketing structure, it appears that producers and marketing institutions have distance and time to the final consumer, including the costs incurred by each marketing institution to deliver the product/fish being marketed based on the channels traversed. This second channel involves two marketing institutions, including; collectors and dealers. For greater clarity, the following can be described quantitatively regarding the total costs, margins and level of income obtained by each institution in table 6 as follows:

Table 6: Analysis of Costs, Margins and Income at the Collector to Retailer Level (Rp/head)

No.	Description	Types of Chickens		
		Ras	Broiler	Not race
01.	Purchases	73.150	64.198	93.474
02.	Marketing costs :			
	•Transport	2.500	1.750	910
	• Cleaning	1.500	1.225	637
	• Sorting	1.350	875	364
	• Preservation	1.125	700	-
	•Packing	2.250	525	-
	• Storage	-	350	-
03.	Total cost	8.725	5.425	1.911
04.	Cost price	81.875	69.623	95.385
05.	Sales price	95.593	90.509	119.650
06.	Income	13.718	20.886	24.265
07.	Marketing margin	18.093	12.302	19,086
08.	Mark-up	30,00	23,00	15,25

Source: *Primary data after processing*

Table 6 above provides an illustration that the level of income obtained by collecting traders is higher than through the first channel. This happens because this channel is short and the selling price is more expensive because the purchasing volume of retailers is smaller than the purchasing volume of sub-district wholesalers. Meanwhile, the cost price and sales price have a mark-up of between 15.25% and 24.26% with different profit levels based on the marketing functions carried out by each marketing institution.

3. Margin and Revenue

Marketing of fresh sea fish production obtained by fishermen through several marketing channels results in different results or business profits for each marketing institution due to marketing function activities, time and costs incurred. This can be seen at the level of margin and income for each marketing channel in table 7 as follows:

Table 7: Analysis of Margin and Revenue in Channel I

No.	Description	Selling price (Rp/ head)	Income (Rp/head)	Cost (Rp/head)	Margin (Rp/head)
1.	Collector Traders	37.470	6.245	8.725	14.970
2.	District Wholesaler	49.834	4.530	7.834	12.364
3.	Regency/city Wholesalers	63.655	5.256	8.565	13.821
4.	Retailer	73.150	6.650	2.845	9.495
	Amount		22.681	27.969	50.650

Source: *Primary data after processing*

Table 7 above describes the amount of income and marketing margin for each channel in the free-range chicken trade system to the final consumer. The highest sales price in this channel is at the retail level at IDR 73,150/head, while the highest margin level is at the collecting trader. The difference in margin income for each channel is due to the activities of marketing functions, costs and the number of marketing institutions. The collecting traders are at the forefront as intermediary traders between breeders and other intermediary traders so that this marketing institution has many marketing function activities which can be seen in table 1. Furthermore, the analysis of margin and income in channel II in table 8 is as follows:

Table 8: Margin and Revenue Analysis in Channel II

No.	Description	Selling price (Rp/Kg)	Income (Rp/Kg)	Cost (Rp/Kg)	Margin (Rp/Kg)
1.	Collector Traders	40.593	9.368	8.725	18.093
2.	Traders listen to retailers	54.582	9.084	4.825	13.909
total			18.452	13.550	32.002

Source: *Primary data after processing*

Table 8 above provides an illustration that the differences in margins, costs and income levels of each marketing institution in each channel are caused by the treatment of the marketing function. For example, collecting traders who sell free-range chickens to retailers have incurred costs of IDR 8,725/head and a sales rate of IDR. 40,593/head. Meanwhile, at the retailer level, the selling price has been set at Rp. 54,582/head, but the costs incurred were Rp. 4,825/head so there is a cost difference of Rp. 3,900/head between collecting traders and retail traders. Next, the margin and income analysis in channel III can be seen as follows:

Table 9: Channel III Margin and Revenue Analysis

No.	Description	Selling price (Rp/ head)	Income (Rp/ head)	Cost (Rp/ head)	Margin (Rp/ head)
1.	Collector Trader	63.655	18.237	4.825	9.159
2.	Regency/City Wholesalers	73.203	4.530	7.834	12.364
3.	Retailer	78.752	10.272	4.825	15.097
Total			33.039	17.484	36.620

Source: *Primary data after processing*

Table 9 above has provided an illustration that the level of expensive sales is at retailers because the free-range chickens received are at the third level from producers. With the stages that goods go through to the final consumer through wholesalers and retailers, the price received by consumers is IDR 78,752 with costs of IDR. 4,825/ head. Meanwhile, the lowest margin level is at the collecting trader level, but the income level is the highest. This occurs because the treatment of the marketing function exceeds that of other marketing institutions. For channel IV with margin and income levels, see the following table:

Table 10: Margin and Revenue Analysis at the Channel IV Retailer Level

No.	Description	Selling price (Rp/ekor)	Income (Rp/ekor)	Cost (Rp/ekor)	Margin (Rp/ekor)
	Manufacturer - Retailer- To the final consumer	49.214	8.202	7.262	15.404

Source; *Primary data after processing*

Table 10 above provides an illustration that the selling price of retailers to final consumers is IDR 49,214/head, and the price from producers to consumers is IDR. 33,750/head, which means there is a difference in the price received by consumers of Rp. 15,464/head. Meanwhile, the selling price of producers in channels I to channel III is an average of Rp. 38,501/head. The price difference received by producers through the short channel is higher than the long channel, which is a theoretical/reference message that effective and efficient marketing of agricultural sector and agricultural sub-sector production is through the short channel.

4. Marketing Channel Efficiency

Marketing efficiency is basically the ratio of marketing output to input. Marketing output is the final sales result received, while marketing input is the funds used to process and transport the product so that it arrives in the hands of consumers. The efficiency of free-range chicken marketing channels from producers to consumers in the Pangkep area to other areas can be seen in table 11 below:

Table 11: Efficiency and Profits of Free-range Chicken Marketing Channels in Pangkep Regency

No.	Channel	efficiency (%)	Profit (Rp/Kg)
1.	I	38,25	22.681
2.	II	24,83	18.452
3.	III	22,20	33.039
4.	IV	14,75	8.202

Source: *Primary data after processing*

Table 11 above shows that the income from marketing fresh sea fish in channel III is IDR 33,039/kg with an efficiency level of 22.20%, while the lowest income is in channel IV amounting to IDR 8,202. There is an assessment of the level of marketing efficiency for fresh sea fish products to find out which channel is more efficient by getting a greater level of profit, although in theory it says that a short marketing channel is an efficient one, but in this study it has been found that the efficient channel is the which results in a higher level of profit.

CONCLUSION

In this research, after being carried out, several study results have been obtained using a matrix cost, margin and income analysis approach so that it can be concluded temporarily as follows:

- 1) The costs, margins and income levels of each marketing agency are different.
- 2) The level of income earned by marketing institutions differs from each other.
- 3) Marketing efficiency of livestock sector products through short marketing channels.
- 4) The high marketing margin for each channel is influenced by the activities of the marketing functions.
- 5) The marketing function influences the level of product quality and increases sales volume.

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